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Sport as a Tool for Curbing Social Vices among Adolescents and Youths in Nigeria: The Critical Role of Parents

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Abstract

The increasing involvement of adolescents and youths in various forms of social vices has become a major social concern in Nigeria today. Rising cases of cultism, drug abuse, cybercrime, armed robbery, kidnapping, banditry, examination malpractices, hooliganism and other anti-social behaviours have continued to threaten national peace, development and social stability. There is a disconnection between parenting, social peace building and national development in Nigeria. Scholars have increasingly advocated the use of sports as an effective strategy for youth engagement, character formation, crime prevention and social peace reconstruction. Sports provide opportunities for positive social interaction, discipline, teamwork, leadership development and constructive utilisation of leisure time. However, the effectiveness of sports as a preventive mechanism largely depends on the support structures surrounding young people, particularly the parents. Parents play critical roles in connecting children to sports, providing emotional and financial support, monitoring peer relationships, reinforcing positive values and modelling socially acceptable behaviors for societal development. This paper examined sports as a viable tool for curbing social vices among adolescents and youths in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on the critical role of parents. This paper concluded that, sports when supported by responsible parenting can be used as a strong tool for combating social vices and restlessness among the youths from the formative years. This paper recommended that parents, educational institutions, sports organisations and policymakers must collaborate to maximise the socialisation process and character building potential of sport for sustainable youth development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Sport, Social Vices, Adolescents, Youths, Parents

Introduction

Adolescence and youth constitute critical stages in human development characterised by rapid physical, emotional, psychological and social changes. These developmental transition often expose young people to both opportunities and vulnerabilities. In Nigeria, concerns have intensified regarding the increasing involvement of adolescents and youths in various forms of social vices, including rape, cultism, alcohol abuse, indecent dressing, terrorism, examination malpractices, cybercrime, bribery, kidnapping, banditry, youth restiveness, drug abuse, child abuse, forgery, corruption, murder, prostitution, hooliganism, gambling, smoking, premarital sexual activities, robbery, pocket picking, violent behaviours, internet fraud and gangsterism among others (Owie & Eshemogie, 2022; Islam, Abubakar et.al., 2023). Such behaviours undermine the well-being of young people and threaten national peace, security as well as socio-economic development. Social vices refer to antisocial behaviors that violate a variety of cultural norms and values (Hassan & Abimbola). They are practices, behaviours or habits generally considered immoral, sinful, rude, taboo, criminal or degrading in the associated society (Islam, Abubakar et. al., 2023). Social vices are all forms of immoral acts indulged in by an individual whose outcome is the opposite of the societal norms (Olayiwola, 2023). Sports on the other hand is a social phenomenon that can transform the society positively. Sports have been integrated with the dynamics of rapidly developing social processes towards the formation of values or norms that are increasingly recognised for their significance in making positive contributions to improving human dignity Hozhabri, et al. (2022). Nations of the world have employed these values to transform worn torn societies into livable environments. Good examples are Liberia and Rwanda. Sports are serve as a means to maintain

physical health and have impacted different spheres of human life as a whole (Bilohur & Andriukaitiene, 2020). Participating in sports activities can help reduce depression, stress, anxiety, increase self-confidence, energy levels, sleep quality and concentration ability (Lu, An, et al., 2022). In addition, participating in sports activities can improve the overall quality of life, develop valuable skills and experience personal growth and self-improvement (Antonova & Merenkov, 2020). Nigeria possesses one of the largest youth populations in Africa. This is a very strong weapon of development that a nation like Nigeria could employ to spark the social and economic development. Young people constitute a significant proportion of the country's population and represent a major resource for national development. However, widespread unemployment, poverty, family instability, peer pressure, inadequate recreational opportunities and weak social support systems have contributed to the vulnerability of many adolescents and youths to deviant behaviours. According to Uyang, Festus et al. (2023), youth involvement in criminal activities as a result of their socio-economic status (poverty and unemployment) is on the increase in Nigeria. Social vices are common among both male and female. Consequently, stakeholders have increasingly sought innovative and preventive approaches capable of redirecting youthful energy toward productive activities.

Sport has emerged as one of the most promising strategies for promoting positive youth outcomes and reducing anti-social behaviours. Sport is an organized, competitive and skillful physical activity requiring commitment and fair play (Dauda, Dominic, et al., 2015). Beyond playing a role in physical growth and individual development, sport also promotes social interaction and integration. According to Oladejo and Soladoye (2025) youth can be provided with the opportunity to learn about having more control and choice in their lives through various sports; they are, in addition, taught life skills and are exposed to better opportunities, which helps them escape the vicious circle of poverty.

Thus, sport can be considered as a coaching process that utilises physical activity to help individuals (including adolescents and youths) achieve their maximum potential. Participation in organised sports provides adolescents and youths with opportunities to acquire life skills such as discipline, perseverance, cooperation, respect for rules, conflict resolution and self-control. These attributes are essential in resisting involvement in behaviours that violate societal norms. In African societies, sports have historically functioned as platforms for transmitting cultural values and fostering social cohesion. Traditional games and modern sporting activities have been used to strengthen communal relationships, promote healthy competition, and instill moral values among young people.

Notwithstanding, the acknowledged benefits of sports and their effectiveness in curbing social vices cannot be separated from the influence of the family environment. Parents remain the primary agents of socialisation and exert considerable influence on the attitudes, behaviours and life choices of their children. Through encouragement, supervision, value orientation, and role modelling, parents can shape adolescents' perceptions of acceptable conduct and determine the extent to which they participate meaningfully in organised activities such as sports. Conversely, parental neglect, poor monitoring, inconsistent discipline and weak emotional attachment may diminish the protective effects of sports participation. This paper therefore examined sport as a strategic tool for curbing social vices among adolescents and youths in Nigeria while highlighting the indispensable role of parents in socialisation through sports and the developmental benefits of sports participation.

Concept of Social Vices among Adolescents and Youths in Nigeria

Social vices refer to behaviours, practices or activities that violate accepted societal norms and values and produce harmful consequences for individuals and society. They encompass acts considered morally unacceptable, legally prohibited or socially destructive. Among adolescents and youths, social vices often manifest through behaviours influenced by developmental challenges, environmental conditions, peer influence, and socio-economic circumstances. In Nigeria today, common social vices among young people include cultism, substance abuse, internet fraud (popularly known as "Yahoo Yahoo"), examination malpractices, kidnapping and banditry, prostitution, hooliganism, armed robbery, cyberbullying and political thuggery. Social vices cause societal instability both within and outside of schools when innocent people, garages, market centers and nearby towns are destroyed, which hinders national growth and development (Hassan & Abimbola).

The proliferation of these behaviours has generated widespread concern among educators, parents, religious leaders, and policymakers. Drug and substance abuse remains one of the most prevalent social problems affecting Nigerian youths. The abuse of alcohol, cannabis, codeine-based products, tramadol and other psychoactive substances has been associated with aggression, poor academic performance, risky sexual behaviours and criminal activities (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC], 2021). Similarly, the increasing sophistication of cybercrime (called Yahoo Yahoo) among Nigerian youths reflects the intersection of technological advancement, unemployment and weakened moral standards and a misplaced educational curriculum that does not address the contemporary challenges in our society. Cultism represents another persistent social vice, particularly within secondary and tertiary institutions. Although, originally associated with ideological movements, cult groups have evolved into violent organizations characterized by intimidation, extortion and

clashes resulting in injury and loss of lives. Examination malpractice, often driven by academic pressure and the desire for success without merit, undermines educational integrity and promotes a culture of dishonesty.

Several factors contribute to youth involvement in social vices in Nigeria. Poverty, unemployment, inadequate parental supervision, peer influence, exposure to violent media content, poor educational opportunities and neighbourhood socialization have all been identified as significant predictors. Family dysfunction, including parental conflict, separation, divorce and absence, further increases susceptibility to deviant behaviours. The consequences of social vices extend beyond individual perpetrators. At the societal level, they contribute to insecurity, reduced productivity, erosion of moral values, and increased expenditure on law enforcement and rehabilitation services. For adolescents and youths, involvement in anti-social behaviours may lead to interrupted educational programme, imprisonment, social stigmatization, health complications, and diminished life opportunities. With these multifaceted consequences, preventive strategies that emphasise positive engagement and youth empowerment are increasingly advocated. Sports constitute one such strategy capable of addressing some of the underlying conditions that predispose young people to social vices.

Sports as a Vehicle for Positive Youth Development

Positive Youth Development (PYD) is an approach that focuses on identifying and nurturing the strengths, competencies, and potentials of young people rather than concentrating solely on deficits and problem behaviours. Within this framework, sports are recognized as contexts through which adolescents and youths can acquire developmental assets necessary for successful adulthood (Holt et al., 2023). Sports participation provides structured environments where young people learn to adhere to rules, respect authority, cooperate with teammates, and manage both success and failure. Through repeated interactions with coaches, teammates, officials, and spectators, participants internalize values such as fairness, honesty, responsibility, and commitment (Fraser-Thomas & Côté, 2016). These experiences contribute to the development of social competence and emotional intelligence that can build a total man for national development.

One of the major ways sports help curb social vices is through the constructive use of leisure time. Idle time has frequently been linked to increased opportunities for delinquent behaviour among adolescents and youths. Organised sports occupy young people's time with purposeful activities that reduce exposure to negative peer influences and environments conducive to anti-social behaviour (Coakley, 2021). Sports also promote a sense of belonging and social connectedness. Adolescents who feel accepted and valued within sports teams are more likely to develop positive identities and less likely to seek validation through deviant peer groups. Team membership provides emotional support networks that can buffer against stress, loneliness, and social exclusion.

Furthermore, participation in sports enhances self-esteem and self-efficacy. Success in skill acquisition and athletic performance reinforces confidence and encourages goal-directed behaviour. Youths who perceive themselves as competent and capable may be better equipped to resist pressures associated with substance abuse, cult recruitment, and criminal involvement. In the Nigerian context, community sports initiatives, school sports programmes, and faith-based sporting activities have demonstrated great potential in promoting social inclusion and redirecting vulnerable youths toward productive lifestyles. Local football competitions, athletics programmes and recreational activities have been used to foster unity, discourage violence, and provide pathways for talent development. However, scholars caution that sports do not automatically produce positive outcomes.

The developmental benefits of sports depend largely on the quality of adult supervision, ethical leadership, programme structure, and the values emphasized within sporting environments (Holt et al., 2023). When sports are characterized by excessive pressure, poor role modelling, or unethical practices, they may inadvertently reinforce negative behaviours. Therefore, the role of significant adults, especially parents, becomes indispensable in ensuring that sports participation translates into meaningful developmental outcomes and contributes effectively to the prevention of social vices among adolescents and youths.

Theoretical Perspective

The use of sports as a preventive strategy against social vices among adolescents and youths can be better understood through relevant theoretical frameworks. There are numerous theories that explain youth behaviour and social development, Social Learning Theory provides strong explanation for how sports participation, supported by effective parenting, can shape socially desirable behaviours.

Social Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory, developed by Bandura (1977), posits that human behaviour is learned through observation, imitation, modelling and reinforcement. According to the theory, children and adolescents acquire attitudes, values and

behavioural patterns by observing significant others, including parents, teachers, coaches, peers and media figures. Behaviour that is rewarded is likely to be repeated, whereas behaviour that is punished tends to diminish. Within the context of sports, adolescents and youths are exposed to numerous opportunities for observational learning. Coaches often serve as mentors who demonstrate discipline, perseverance, respect for rules and emotional regulation. Teammates reinforce acceptable conducts through group norms, while parents model attitudes toward fair play, commitment, and sportsmanship. Through these interactions, young people internalize socially acceptable behaviours that discourage involvement in anti-social activities (Aremu & Adewale, 2021).

Social Learning Theory, however, also suggests that sports environments can reinforce undesirable behaviours if aggression, cheating, substance use or violence are normalised. Consequently, parental guidance and supervision becomes essential in helping adolescents interpret sporting experiences appropriately and distinguish between acceptable competitiveness and deviant conduct.

Sports and the Prevention of Social Vices in Nigeria

Sports have increasingly been recognised as effective tools for crime prevention, peacebuilding and youth empowerment across the globe. Participation in sports activities has long been recognized for its potential to positively influence youth development across physical, social, and psychological domains (Dey, 2024). In Nigeria, where social vices among adolescents and youths continue to attract public concern, sports offer structured opportunities capable of redirecting youthful energies toward productive pursuits.

1. **Structured engagement:** One of the primary mechanisms through which sports reduce social vices is through structured engagement. Participation in organised sporting activities occupies leisure time that might otherwise be spent in environments associated with delinquency. Adolescents and youths involved in school and community sports programmes are less likely to engage in substance abuse, cultism and violent activities than their non-participating counterparts. Sports also facilitate the development of life skills necessary for resisting deviant influences. Skills such as decision-making, goal setting, teamwork, self-discipline, leadership and conflict resolution are frequently acquired through sports participation. These competencies enable young people to cope effectively with peer pressure and other social challenges.

2. **Social integration and inclusion:** Furthermore, sports promote social integration and inclusion. Adolescents from diverse ethnic, religious and socio-economic backgrounds interact within shared sporting spaces, thereby reducing prejudice and fostering mutual understanding. This is particularly important in Nigeria's multicultural society, where youth-related conflicts occasionally assume ethnic and religious dimensions.

3. **Improved psychological well-being:** Sports participation has also been associated with improved psychological well-being. Regular involvement in physical activities reduces stress, anxiety and depression while enhancing self-esteem and emotional stability. Youths who possess healthy coping mechanisms are generally less vulnerable to behaviours such as drug abuse and aggression. Studies have shown that sports participation has the capabilities to improve mental health of individuals and good for managing adolescents and youths that are challenged.

4. **Talent discovery and economic empowerment:** Another significant contribution of sports lies in talent discovery and economic empowerment. Nigeria has produced internationally acclaimed athletes whose achievements have inspired countless young people. Sports scholarships, professional careers, coaching opportunities, and sports entrepreneurship provide legitimate alternatives to criminal activities and unemployment (Ajayi & Oyetunde, 2022). Community-based sports initiatives have equally demonstrated potential for youth transformation. Programmes organised by schools, religious institutions, non-governmental organizations and local communities often use football, athletics, volleyball and indigenous games to engage vulnerable youths and promote civic values. Such interventions have been reported to strengthen social bonds and reduce youth involvement in anti-social behaviours.

Nevertheless, sports are not inherently transformative. Their effectiveness depends on the quality of programme design, ethical leadership, availability of facilities and active involvement of families and communities. Without appropriate guidance, competitive pressures and poor sports cultures may undermine intended developmental outcomes.

The Critical Role of Parents in Curbing Social Vices through Sports

The family is the first and the most basic institution of every society for developing the child's potentials in all aspect of life (Imbur, Iroegbu, et. al., 2020). Parents play a key role in the youth sports educational experience; they are responsible for the introduction of their children to physical or sporting education and their involvement has been associated with sport participation in early stages (Bonavolontà, Cataldi, et. al., 2021). Parents are the first and most influential agent of socialisation in the lives of children and adolescents. Their values, attitudes, expectations and parenting practices significantly shape behavioural outcomes throughout development. Consequently, the success of sports as a strategy for

curbing social vices depends mostly on the nature and extent of parental involvement. Following, are some roles of parents in using sports to curb social vices among adolescents and youths.

1. **Encouraging Participation in Sports:** Parents often determine whether children are introduced to sports and recreational activities in most cases. By enrolling children in school teams, community clubs and structured sporting programmes, parents create opportunities for positive engagement and skill development. Research has consistently shown that parental encouragement significantly predicts adolescents' participation in physical activity and organized sports (Fraser-Thomas & Côté, 2016). In Nigeria, where academic achievement is frequently prioritised over extracurricular activities, some parents perceive sports as distractions from education. Such perceptions may limit opportunities for youths to benefit from the developmental advantages associated with sports participation. Parents who appreciate the educational and social value of sports are more likely to support balanced development among their children.

2. **Providing Emotional and Financial Support:** Active participation in sports often requires emotional encouragement and financial investment. Parents contribute by purchasing sporting equipment, paying registration fees, facilitating transportation, and attending competitions. Emotional support reinforces adolescents' confidence, motivation, and persistence, particularly during periods of failure or disappointment. Parental support enhances youths' commitment to sports and strengthens the positive outcomes associated with participation. Adolescents who perceive their parents as supportive tend to exhibit higher self-esteem, better emotional adjustment and lower tendencies toward deviant behaviours.

3. **Monitoring Peer Relationships and Behaviour:** Parental monitoring constitutes one of the strongest protective factors against adolescent delinquency. Effective monitoring involves knowing children's friends, understanding their activities, maintaining communication and setting clear behavioural expectations. Sports environments expose young people to diverse peer networks. While many peer relationships formed through sports are positive, some may exert negative influences. Parents who remain actively involved in their children's sporting experiences are better positioned to identify potentially harmful associations and provide appropriate guidance.

4. **Reinforcing Moral Values:** Sports provide numerous teachable moments through which parents can reinforce values such as honesty, humility, fairness, respect, and perseverance. Conversations about winning and losing, respect for officials, and adherence to rules help adolescents connect sporting experiences with broader life lessons. When parents emphasize ethical conduct over mere performance outcomes, young people are more likely to develop strong moral identities and reject behaviours inconsistent with societal expectations.

5. **Serving as Positive Role Models:** Children learn not only through instruction but also through observation. Parents who demonstrate integrity, self-control, respect for others, and healthy lifestyles provide behavioural templates that adolescents are likely to emulate. Conversely, parental involvement characterized by aggression toward officials, excessive pressure to win, or tolerance of unethical conduct may undermine the character-building potential of sports. Therefore, parents must model the values they seek to instill in their children.

Challenges to Effective Parental Involvement in Sports

Parental involvement in youths' sporting experiences is very important. Despite the importance, several barriers hinder effective involvement by parents. Some of the challenges are:

1. **Economic hardship:** One major challenge is economic hardship. High levels of poverty and unemployment limit many parents' ability to provide financial support for sporting activities. Costs associated with equipment, transportation, uniforms and competition fees may discourage sustained participation.

2. **Time constraints:** This also constitute significant obstacles. Parents who are engaged in demanding occupations may struggle to supervise children's sporting activities, unable to maintain active communication regarding their children's sporting experiences and unable to attend competitions.

3. **Negative perceptions of sports:** Another challenge is the wrong or negative perception of sports by parents. Some parents continue to regard sports as inferior to academic pursuits and therefore discourage participation, especially when professional athletic careers appear uncertain (Ajayi & Oyetunde, 2022).

4. **Inadequate sporting facilities and poorly organised programmes:** Parents' concerns concerning safety, poor coaching practices and limited opportunities for progression may reduce parents' willingness to invest in sports participation.

Finally, declining family cohesion and changing family structures may weaken supervision and support systems essential for maximizing the protective effects of sports against social vices.

Conclusion

The increasing prevalence of social vices among adolescents and youths in Nigeria presents serious challenges to national development, social stability and the future well-being of the country's young population. Issues such as cultism, substance abuse, cybercrime, examination malpractice, hooliganism and violent behaviours continue to undermine efforts toward sustainable development and social progress. In conclusion, this paper has demonstrated that sports possess enormous potential as preventive and developmental tools capable of redirecting youthful energies toward socially desirable outcomes. Through structured participation, sports facilitate the acquisition of life skills, promote social inclusion, enhance psychological well-being, strengthen self-esteem and provide constructive alternatives to delinquent behaviours. Sports also foster values such as discipline, teamwork, respect, perseverance and responsibility, all of which serve as protective factors against social vices. However, the transformative potential of sports does not occur automatically.

By taking an active role in their children's lives and supporting their participation in sports, parents can help them develop valuable skills, values, and healthy habits, ultimately contributing to a more positive and fulfilling life free from social vices. As a result, efforts aimed at curbing social vices among Nigerian adolescents and youths should not focus solely on punitive measures. Greater emphasis should be placed on preventive strategies that strengthen families, promote positive youth engagement and create supportive sporting environments. When parents, schools, communities and governments work collaboratively, sports can become a powerful mechanism for nurturing responsible citizens and fostering a safer, more productive society.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

- i. **Integration of structured sports programmes into the educational system:** There is a need for the integration of structured sports programmes into the educational system. Schools should regard sports as an essential component of holistic education rather than merely extracurricular activities. School administrators should organise regular inter-house sports competitions, intramural programmes and community-based sporting events that promote participation among all students irrespective of ability levels. Such programmes can serve as preventive platforms against delinquent behaviours by engaging students constructively and fostering discipline.
- ii. **Reinforced culture of sports through grassroots sports development:** Governments at federal, state and local levels should invest in grassroots sports development. Bring back the culture of sports through local government donations, grants and subvention to sponsorships sports development at the primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria. The provision of safe and accessible sporting facilities in schools and communities would encourage more youth participation. Investments should include the renovation of existing facilities, training of qualified coaches and establishment of youth sports centres, particularly in underserved communities where adolescents may be more vulnerable to social vices.
- iii. **Parental education programmes:** Parental education programmes should be strengthened. Many Nigerian parents still perceive sports as distractions from academic pursuits. Educational campaigns should therefore be reinforced to enlighten parents on the developmental benefits of sports, including their role in promoting discipline, resilience, social competence and emotional well-being. Parent-teacher associations, religious institutions and community organisations can serve as channels for disseminating such information.
- iv. **Training of coaches and sports administrators:** Coaches and sports administrators should be trained in positive youth development principles. Beyond technical expertise, coaches require competencies in mentoring, communication, safeguarding and value-based leadership. Youth sports programmes should intentionally teach life skills and emphasise character development together with athletic performance.
- v. **Collaborative partnerships among various stake holders:** Collaborative partnerships between families, schools, sports organisations, non-governmental organizations and policymakers should be encouraged. Such partnerships can facilitate the design and implementation of comprehensive interventions targeting vulnerable youths. Community sports initiatives can be integrated with counselling services, mentorship programmes and vocational development opportunities to address multiple risk factors simultaneously.
- vi. **Policies should prioritize inclusiveness and accessibility:** Future policies should prioritise inclusiveness and accessibility. Adolescents and youths from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, those living with disabilities and those residing in rural areas should be included in the opportunities to participate in sports. Inclusive sports policies can contribute to social cohesion, reduce marginalization and strengthen community resilience.

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